

OPTIMAL TRUNCATION CRITERION FOR COMPOUND PARABOLIC COLLECTORS: A THERMODYNAMIC JUSTIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

CPCs are one of the most studied solar concentrators due to their flexibility and their capability to reach the thermodynamic limit. However, the main drawback of these systems is their height, so several truncation criteria had been proposed to reduce its height up to half of the full CPC. Originally, all those criteria were just geometrically justified and fully discussed in the literature, but recently the Rincón's criterion, was independently deduced with the use of the constructal law (therefore re-named here as a maximum acceptance angle, MAA), which raised several questions regarding if this was the most appropriate criterion for CPCs designs. In the present work, a further discussion of the truncation criteria is done, determining the variation of the geometric parameters (sveltteness and reflector area-aperture area ratio), the optical parameters (average number of reflections and etendue), and a second law analysis (entropy generation rate, optimal temperature, and efficiency) as a function of the concentration ratio. As a result, it is demonstrated that the MAA criterion is the most appropriate from a thermodynamic and geometric point of view, since the height, the average number of reflections, the etendue loss and the entropy generation rate are minimum, which leads to higher efficiency.

Keywords: CPC, solar energy, truncation, entropy generation, optimization

NOMENCLATURE

C_g	concentration ratio
Sv	sveltteness
$r_{m,a}$	reflector area-aperture area ratio
n	average number of reflections
$\%U_{loss}$	etendue loss
$N_{s,min}$	entropy generation number
$T_{r,opt}$	optimum receiver temperature
η_{opt}	optimum efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

The origin of compound parabolic concentrators (CPC) can be traced back to the mid-'60s by the developments of different researchers in the URSS [1], Germany [2], and the US [3], who independently described an optical system, unlike traditional systems, based on the optimal transfer of radiation, even if this implies forming aberrations, so the name non-imaging optics was coined [4]. This new optics allow reaching the thermodynamic limit for solar concentrators [5], and their potential as collectors of solar energy was pointed out by Winston [6].

Today, there is already a wide development of CPCs for solar applications, and several geometries have been generated that take advantage of non-imaging optics to concentrate solar energy on receivers of different shapes (circular, square, triangular, wedge, flat...) [4], [7]. One problem with CPCs is that the ratio of height vs the receiver's area (sveltteness) is too large, i.e. these concentrators are too high, and this ultimately limits their application [4].

For several years, different truncation criteria have been proposed to decrease the total height [8]–[11], although all have been developed from a purely geometrical perspective. However, recently, the use of *Bejan's Constructal Law* demonstrated geometrically one of those criteria seems to be beneficial from an energy point of view [12], but the urgency to validate it through a more formal optical and thermodynamic basis is needed, and fulfilled in the present work.

2. THE DESCRIPTION OF THE CPC

The CPC has the advantage of reducing or eliminating the tracking needs using a trough with two sections of a rotated parabola facing each other, as shown in Fig. 1, where $2a$ is the aperture area, $2a'$ is the receiver's area, h is the height and θ_0 is the half-acceptance angle. The subscript t stands for the truncated parameter.

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC OF A CPC.

The CPC's can accept incoming radiation over a relatively wide range of angles. All the incoming rays entering at $2a$ within the acceptance angle will be reflected by the mirrors onto the receiver. The most important parameter of all the concentration systems is the concentration ratio, defined by $C_g = \frac{2a}{2a'}$, however, as shown in Fig. 1, the upper part of the mirrors is almost vertical, and does not contribute significantly to the concentration ratio, so to save material, and to reduce the total height of the CPC, it is usually truncated.

2.1 Geometric parameters

The parametric equations to describe a CPC are

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = \frac{2a'(1+\sin\theta_0)\cos t}{1-\sin(t-\theta_0)} \\ y(t) = \frac{2a'(1+\sin\theta_0)\sin t}{1-\sin(t-\theta_0)} \end{cases}, \quad t \in \left[0, \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_0\right] \quad (1)$$

and for the full CPC can be demonstrated [13] that

$$C_g = \frac{1}{\sin\theta_0} \quad (2)$$

With the parametric equations (1), the svelteness Sv (height-aperture ratio) and the reflector area-aperture area ratio $r_{m,a}$ can be determined by

$$Sv = \frac{y(t)}{2x(t)-2a'} \quad (3)$$

$$r_{m,a} = \frac{2 \int_0^{t_{max}} \sqrt{(x')^2 + (y')^2} dt}{2x(t)-2a'} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Optical-energy related parameters

The energy that reaches the absorber can be described by a relation $\dot{Q}_u \sim G_b C_g \eta_o$, where G_b is the beam solar radiation and η_o is the optical efficiency, being a function of the average number of reflections n in the mirrors with reflectivity ρ as $\eta_o \sim \rho^n$. Originally, the average number of reflections were studied by Rabl [8], where it is shown that reducing the value of n lead to an increase of the useful energy in the receiver. A summary of Rabl's equations for n can be found in [14].

However, the most important parameter in optics is the etendue U , defined as geometric quantity that measures the amount of "place" available for light to pass [7], as a measure of the transmitted power along a beam of light. For 2D systems, the etendue is defined as [4], [7], [13]

$$U = 2A n_{ref} \sin\theta \cos\phi \quad (5)$$

Where A is the area where the light passes, n_{ref} is the refractive index, θ is the solid angle where light enters in A and ϕ is the incidence angle. For full CPCs, the etendue is conserved. If a great loss of etendue occurs, the system will not be properly capturing the light, so the percentage of etendue loss can be defined as

$$\%U_{loss} = \frac{U_{in}-U_{out}}{U_{in}} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

2.3 Entropy related parameters in a CPC

As described by Bejan [15], the minimization of the entropy generation rate, implies the maximization of the useful power. The thermal solar energy processes are always accompanied by the generation of entropy. Considering an isothermal concentrator, the entropy generation includes the heat transfer coefficient U_r , the ambient temperature T_0 , and the apparent sun temperature as an exergy source $T^* = \frac{3}{4}T_s$, as suggested by Petela [16], described by

$$\dot{S}_{gen} = \frac{U_r(2a')(T_r-T_0)}{T_0} - \frac{\dot{Q}_u}{T^*} + \frac{\dot{Q}_u - U_r(2a')(T_r-T_0)}{T_r} \quad (7)$$

In the limit case, the minimum dimensionless entropy generation rate, or the entropy generation number, is modeled by

$$N_{s,min} = \frac{\dot{S}_{gen,min}}{U_r(2a')} = 2(\sqrt{\theta_{max}} - 1) - \frac{\theta_{max}-1}{\theta^*} \quad (8)$$

where $\theta_{max} = \frac{T_{r,max}}{T_0}$, and $\theta^* = \frac{T^*}{T_0}$. The stagnation temperature $T_{r,max}$ lead to the possibility of determining the optimum receiver temperature to attain the minimum entropy generation rate by

$$T_{r,opt} = \sqrt{T_{r,max} T_0} \quad (9)$$

and the optimum efficiency for minimum irreversibility

$$\eta_{opt} = \frac{\sqrt{\theta_{max}}}{\sqrt{\theta_{max}+1}} \quad (10)$$

2.4 Truncation of the CPC

As mentioned previously, one of the disadvantages of the CPC's is the height of the concentrator, however, as seen in Fig. 1, the upper part of the mirrors does not contribute substantially to C_g . For this reason, it is recommended to eliminate a portion of the mirror to reduce the height; but on the other hand, C_g will be reduced too.

Winston, Rabl, and O'Gallagher recommend truncating the CPCs about half the fully developed height [6], [8], [10] (*Winston's criterion*), while it can be found that some CPC can be truncated up to 2/3 the full height to reduce the loss in C_g . On an independent basis, Rincón et al. [11] have proposed to truncate the CPCs up to $3\theta_0$, because at this angle, the mirror will not block the light in the half-acceptance angle range $\pm\theta_0$. However, further discussion of the thermal performance of CPCs is required for an objective comparison of the truncation criterions.

All these criteria were established only through a purely geometrical approach, but *Rincón's criterion* was recently demonstrated by González-Mora et al. through the *Constructal Law* on an energy basis [12]. As a result, several researchers had communicated encouraging to re-name the criterion to *Rincón-Mora criterion* or *maximum acceptance-angle criterion* since a different approach was used to find the same result. Here, the *maximum acceptance angle criterion* is coined; however, as Rincón et al. were the first to propose it [11], the present author suggests keeping in mind the contribution that was made geometrically some years ago.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To compare the performance of the CPCs for the different truncation criteria, the Eqs. (1) to (10) were varied for different C_g values. The results are described below for the full CPC, and for truncated CPC's, the proposed *maximum acceptance-angle criterion (MAA)* and *Winston's criterion* for half the full height are considered.

3.1 Geometric results

In Fig. 2, the svelteness Sv and the reflector area-aperture area $r_{m,a}$ are plotted as a function of the concentration ratio C_g . As can be seen, *Winston's criterion* (red line) reduces the height of the CPCs, but the *MAA's criterion* (blue line) reduces even further the height in comparison with the full CPC (black line). Here, a general comment must be done for all the plots, since *Winston's criterion* reduces the concentration ratio one must find the intersection of the blue curve with the green curves to read the desired parameter, while the *MAA's criterion* attains no reduction in concentration ratio since a new acceptance angle must be determined to keep the original C_g value, and parameters can be read directly. So, geometrically, the MAA criterion results are beneficial due to Sv and $r_{m,a}$ reduction with no C_g loss.

FIGURE 2: SVELTENESS AND REFLECTOR-APERTURE RATIO OF THE FULL AND TRUNCATED CPC.

3.2 Optical results

The average number of reflections and the etendue loss are shown in Fig. 3 and can be read like the previous plots. As in Fig. 2, the black line is for the full CPC, the red line for *Winston's criterion* and the blue line for *MAA's criterion*. As can be seen, the Winston criterion considerably reduces the average number

of reflections, but the MAA criterion reduces even more the average number of reflections, being the same for C_g between 2 and 5. An interesting behavior occurs for the etendue loss, since the MAA criterion results beneficial for $C_g > 2.28$. In view of these results, the optical efficiency will be maximum for the CPC that is truncated with the MAA criterion due to a greater reduction of n .

FIGURE 3: AVERAGE NUMBER OF REFLECTIONS AND ETENDUE LOSS OF THE FULL AND TRUNCATED CPC.

3.3 Entropy results

The final, and most important parameters to demonstrate the validity of the MAA criterion are the entropy related parameters, since a design with a lower entropy generation rate, leads to higher efficiency. In Fig. 4, the dimensionless entropy generation rate can be read as the previous plots. The black line is for the full CPC, the red line for *Winston's criterion*, and the blue line for *MAA's criterion*. Again, the N_s is minimum in the case of the MAA criterion, so this lead to a less irreversible CPC.

FIGURE 4: ENTROPY GENERATION NUMBER OF THE FULL AND TRUNCATED CPC.

In Fig. 5, the optimum temperature of the CPCs is displayed. Now, the optimum temperature profiles for the full and MAA are the same. This is due to the no reduction of the concentration ratio of the CPC. And in Fig. 6, the optimum collector efficiency plot shows that the highest profiles are for the MAA criterion, and even higher than for the full CPC. This result may seem a bit contradictory, but it is not. By truncating with the MAA criterion, the average reflections (Fig. 3) within the concentrator optics have been significantly reduced, so that the light travels shorter optical paths without suffering large attenuations. In the same way, this criterion leads to a decrease in entropy generation (Fig. 4) with an optimum temperature equal to that of a full CPC

(Fig. 5). It is this combination that allows CPCs using the MAA criterion to have superior performance.

FIGURE 5: OPTIMUM TEMPERATURE OF THE FULL AND TRUNCATED CPC.

FIGURE 6: OPTIMUM EFFICIENCY OF THE FULL AND TRUNCATED CPC.

4. CONCLUSION

The CPC has several advantages for concentration systems; principally the possibility to get mid temperature ranges with a fixed concentrator, however, its height is the major drawback for its application. As a result, several truncation criteria had been proposed to increase its use, but up to date, all had been justified by its height reduction, so an urgency to compare those criteria with a thermodynamic basis was needed. As a result of the analysis, the geometry of the CPCs can be optimized by using the MAA criterion, since it is possible to generate low-height geometries, without losing concentration, minimizing the entropy generation rate and maximizing the efficiency.

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